

UZBEK EMBROIDERY AS PRICELESS CULTURAL HERITAGE OF UZBEK PEOPLE

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Abstract

This article describes the historical peculiarities of Uzbek embroidery art. Moreover, it gives information about the origin of embroidery as one of the ancient branches of applied art in the world. Embroidery art is mentioned as a priceless cultural heritage of Uzbek people.

Key words: *embroidery, applied art, culture, cultural heritage, archeology.*

Embroidery is one of the ancient branches of applied art. Archeological findings show that embroidery is ancient in almost all nations, and that it developed under the influence of climate, natural conditions, and the culture, art, and professions of each nation. The appearance of embroidery is connected with the appearance of seams and stitches in leather clothes. It is associated with the transition from stone to bone beads to metal beads, as well as weaving, dyeing and other works. The development of embroidery can be observed in the image of embroidery in ancient Asian, European, and American cultural monuments, literary sources, as well as in preserved examples of embroidery. The oldest copies of embroidery products have not been preserved. In nations where embroidery is developed, it was greatly influenced by fine art. For example, English embroidery of the 11th century depicts battle scenes. Russian embroidery of the 12th century clearly shows the influence of Byzantine icon art. From the 14th century in China, the embroidery, known as "xiuhua" (needle painting), is stylistically close to the genre of silk dreamscapes.

Uzbek national embroidery is one of the most ancient types of folk crafts, which arose as a result of the people's desire to make their life beautiful. Embroidery has been used since ancient times in the decoration of clothes and items, as well as in the preparation of decorative items.

Our embroidery art is famous not only in our country, but also abroad. *Kirpich, suzana, zardevor, gulkurpa, choyshab* etc. made by Uzbek embroidery masters are sold not only in Uzbekistan but also in several foreign countries, such as France, Italy, Japan, Germany, Belgium, America, India. Many examples of which have been collected in museums of applied art and have become permanent exhibits.

Until now, the products have been surprising people with their unique beauty and variety of elegant decorations. Artistic embroidery has a long history, as evidenced by archaeological finds and written sources. Uzbek embroidery has developed together with all other professions in connection with the climate, natural conditions, and environment. Through the miniatures of the 14th and 15th centuries, it is possible to see the development of embroidery from a long time ago. The Spanish ambassador Rui Ganzalem de Clavijo recorded in his diary that he saw Uzbek national embroidery decorations in the palace of Amir Temur.

Uzbek embroidery was enriched and developed under the influence of the embroidery of neighboring nations. If we pay attention to Uzbek embroidery, we will find the methods of Indian, Chinese, Russian, Kazakh, Kyrgyz and Tajik embroidery.

The color images in Suzana actually speak of values and traditions. As soon as a girl child is born in every Uzbek or Tajik family, long-term rituals are performed in order to adjust her dowry. Later, when the girl grows up, she herself embroiders and restores her dowry. The profession of painting taught to young girls by their mothers or grandmothers also played an important role in the creation of these sayings.

To conclude, we can say that embroidery products are the proud of Uzbek people. And it has a long historical and cultural value.

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